
Rural Transformation in Maharashtra: A Case Study of Two Villages in Ahmednagar District

Rajendra M. Shingate

Department of Geography,

Dr. Patangrao Kadam Arts and Commerce College, Pen - Raigad.

Corresponding Author - Rajendra M. Shingate

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Abstract:

To study the rural transformation of Maharashtra, two villages of Ahmednagar district have been taken into consideration. To study the spatial disparity in development for India, Maharashtra and for villages, the composite index method has been used. It has been concluded that as compare to Pimpalgaon Malvi, Hivre Bajar village is more developed.

Introduction:

Rural development is a complex phenomenon covering a wide spectrum of activities meant to uplift the condition of people, especially the poor people, living in rural areas. The aspects of development for rural people can be classified into five broad groups 1. Health 2. Education 3. Agriculture 4. Housing 5. Industries. In any scheme of rural development, the top priority has been given to poverty alleviation, increased employment opportunities and elimination of inequality. Robert S. McNamara, former President of the World Bank, states, “Development is meaningless if it does not in the end enhance the lives of individual human being, particularly those individuals whose circumstances are so wretchedly deprived as to constitute an intolerable insult to human dignity itself”. (Robert S. McNamara, 1980).

World Bank publication defines rural development as, “Improving living standards of the masses of the low-income population residing in rural areas making the process of rural development self-sustaining” (Lele, 1975).

India is predominantly a rural country. According to 2001 census more than 70 percent people are living in rural areas, earning one-fourth of the national income. Near about 700 million people living in 600,000 villages in India. Villagers are deprived from many basic services. Mass illiteracy, sanitation problem, health transportation, telecommunication facility, market are the problems present in rural India. These facilities are available in the cities; therefore, people migrate to the cities to enjoy the above-mentioned facilities. An attempt has been made to study socio-economic situation of two villages of Maharashtra.

Methodology:

Composite index method used to see the level of development. Two villages from Ahmednagar district has been taken for the study. Socio-economic survey of households of Hivre Bajar and Pimpalgaon Malvi were conducted by taking 200 households from each village. Random sampling method has been used to select the sample. To analyze the results different cartographic methods have been used.

Data Sources:

The data used for this study have been collected from different secondary sources viz. District Census Handbook, Census of India 2001 and other publications of Census of India. The primary data have been collected from village *Hivre Bajar & Pimpalgaon Malvi*

with the help of well- structured questionnaires.

Objectives:

- 1) To study the composite index of Maharashtra and Ahmednagar.
- 2) To identify the composite index and development of demographic, social and economic aspects of the study area.

Study Area:

For present study two villages from western Maharashtra has been selected. The study area, Hivre Bajar and Pimpalgaon Malvi is located in Ahmednagar district. The study areas are dry villages located in the Ahmednagar district of Maharashtra. Both villages are 13 k.m. close to Ahmednagar city of Maharashtra.

Google- Earth view of Hivrebajar and Pimpalgaon Malvi

Location Map

Variables used for calculation of composite index:

1. Total fertility rate
2. Sex ratio
3. Age at marriage for girls
4. Infant mortality rate
5. Life expectancy
6. Male literacy level
7. Female literacy level
8. Male work participation rate
9. Female work participation rate
10. Urbanization
11. Percent people below poverty line
12. Percent people having Pucca house
13. Percent people used LPG
14. Percent people used electricity
15. Percent people have separate toilet

facility

16. Percent people used tap water and
17. Percent people have separate latrine facility.

District wise Composite Index of Maharashtra:

The composite index is lowest for Gadchiroli (score 34) and highest for Pune district (score 60). Gondia, Chandrapur and Nandurbar districts scored between 38 and 42. The medium level development occurred in central Maharashtra range between 43 and 49. Majority of the districts of Western Maharashtra is showing higher development than that of National average (42). Eastern districts

like Nagpur and Wardha as well as Southeastern districts Latur are indicating higher development than national average. More Developmental planning should be

given to Gadchiroli, Chandrapur, and Nandurbar and Gondia predominantly tribal districts by the Government and NGOs.

Tahsil wise Composite Index of Ahmednagar district:

Above map indicates development of Ahmednagar district. Ahmednagar and Shirampur tahsils are top of the list of demographic, social and economic aspects of development. Akole Parner and Pathardi tahsil need to develop their development indices. In case of Ahmednagar district, from where the study villages have been taken, the level of

rurality is showing that most of the places are indicating high rural proportion and not a single place is showing extreme non-rural areas. Akole, Sangamner, Rahata, Karjat, Pathardi, Srigonda has more than 80 percent rurality. Only Ahmednagar and Shirampur are having percentage of rural population less than 50 percent. This shows that the district of study area is an example of least rural development.

Variables used for calculation of composite index for two study villages:

Sr. No.	Name of the variables	Index	
		Hivrebajar	Pimpalgaon Malvi
	Census aspects		
1	Sex ratio	0.96	0.80
2	Male literacy level	0.78	0.72
3	Female literacy level	0.72	0.64
4	Male work participation rate	0.80	0.77
5	Female work participation rate	0.75	0.61
	First hand survey aspects		
6	Age at marriage for girls	0.71	0.62
7	Birth rate	0.52	0.48
8	Death rate	0.49	0.38
9	Income of Household	0.64	0.61
10	Occupation Index	0.22	0.28
11	Percent people having pucca house	0.35	0.28
12	Percent people used LPG	0.14	0.16
13	Percent people used electricity	0.34	0.24
14	Percent people used tap connection	0.12	0.08
15	Percent people have separate toilet facility	0.11	0.06
16	Percent people have separate latrine facility	0.07	0.00
17	Percent people have knowledge about HIV/AIDS	0.96	0.92
18	Percent people have participated last election	0.88	0.68
19	Percent female have participate in decision making in the house	0.74	0.64
	COMPOSITE INDEX	0.542	0.472

In case of composite index of village level is concern; Hivre Bajar shows higher transformation than that for Pimpalgaon Malvi. Composite index of Hivre Bajar and Pimpalgaon Malvi are 0.542 and 0.472 respectively. In Pimpalgaon Malvi sex ratio, female literacy level, age at marriage for girl is less than Hivre Bajar. On the contrary fertility is higher than that of Hivre Bajar. This means the indicators which are showing the development of any area is indicating worsen situation in Pimpalgaon Malvi. As per the method, Hivre Bajar has

high level of development index while Pimpalgaon Malvi has medium level of development index.

The rural transformation in Maharashtra has occurred in different aspects like socio- economic, per capita income and land use pattern. An attempt has been made to see the transformation in land use, people engaged in different economic activities, literacy, sex ratio, proportion of land under irrigation in two villages named, Hivre Bajar and Pimpalgaon Malvi.

Conclusion:

Maharashtra is one of the advanced states in India in terms of income, industry, urbanization, female literacy etc. But the rural situation is dilapidated in some aspects. Hivre Bajar is one of the developed villages in Maharashtra, awarded with ideal village prize in 1995. But in many aspects it is underdeveloped, like education, transportation and health. While Pimpalgaon Malvi is the village also has problems of infrastructure, illiteracy, education, and social amenities. Probably Mahatma Gandhi was the first Indian leader who publicly said that real India dwells in village. Unless and until we achieve the development of villages, we cannot develop India.

In both the villages, Hivre Bajar and Pimpalgaon Malvi more than 70 percent people are engaged in agricultural activities. In Hivre Bajar 50 percent people are literate SSC and above but in Pimpalgaon Malvi this proportion is only 27 percent. In Hivre Bajar 75 percent people owned more than 4 acre of land but in Pimpalgaon Malvi this proportion is only 34 percent. In Hivre Bajar 83 percent houses are having better condition and in Pimpalgaon Malvi 70 percent people are having better housing. In Hivre Bajar 72 percent people are using fuel for cooking this proportion is more than 90 percent in Pimpalgaon Malvi. Still people are using kerosene for light. This percentage is 21 and 36 percent for Hivre Bajar and Pimpalgaon Malvi respectively. In both the villages more than 90 percent people are taking opinion of female in the major

decision. In both the villages near about 90 percent people are aware about HIV/AIDs. In Hivre Bajar 25 percent people tested for HIV/AID but in Pimpalgaon Malvi this proportion is only 4 percent. Hivre Bajar village has got the award of Ideal village by the Government in 1995. The above study shows that even in ideal village is lacking in many aspects like use of fuel wood, Kerosene, agrarian occupation etc. This shows that the pace of rural transformation in Maharashtra is very slow. If rural India will transformed with development of agro –based industries and self-entrepreneurship etc. then it is possible to develop the rural India.

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